

Autumn-Sown Organically Managed Faba Bean-Oat Intercrops to enhance Crop Resilience

Problem

In organic faba beans cultivation success is often determined by two main factors: effective weed management; and limiting the impact of diseases.

Solution

According to experience in the Swiss pedoclimate, intercropping faba beans with oats (Figure 1) can increase yield resilience for winter- and spring-sown crops. This is achieved through the ability of intercrops to reduce weed and pest pressure. The total yield also tends to be higher with mixed crops compared to monocrops; since both oats and beans are harvested (together).

Benefits

In this intercrop, oats quickly germinate to establish soil cover, reducing (late) weed growth; and reducing aphid numbers, which also serve as virus vectors. Oats has a more 'neutral' impact environmentally on the crop rotation compared to other cereal crops; better suppressing weeds; even when mechanical weed control (harrowing) is not possible due to unfavourable conditions. Also, if other (cereal) crop fail, oats can compensate for this loss.

Applicability box

Theme

Intercropping Legumes and Cereal.

Keywords

Intercropping; Faba Beans; Oats; Yield Resilience; Organic Agriculture.

Context

Central Europe.

Application time

Autumn/Spring sowing

Period of impact

Cultivation period; and across whole crop rotation.

Equipment

Standard equipment; capability to weigh/mix oat & bean seed.

Best in

Organic agriculture.

Figure 1. Left: Autumn sown faba beans with oats, harrow in the background and Right: Spring sown faba beans with oats. Photos: Matthias Klaiss, FiBL.

Practical recommendation

- **Seed mix:** a good mix to start is 80-90 % of faba beans, and 30-40 % Oats. % = of usual monocrops stand density.
- **Sowing seed mix** at 12 cm row distance, seeding depth 3-4 cm, 4-5 cm in sandy soil. (This is for Switzerland; and needs optimised for other countries/regions).

- **Synthetic nitrogen (N) fertiliser** is not required to facilitate production/N accumulation (by legume crop).
- **Autumn-sown oats and beans will ripen at the same time.** Spring-sowing requires late-maturing oat varieties for simultaneous ripening with the faba bean.
- **Oats N-content may be reduced** (compared to monocropped oats), due to limited N-fertiliser use.
- **The combine harvester needs adjusted** to harvest the main cash crop, i.e., faba bean.
- **The proportion of legumes in the harvest can vary** (averaged between 50-60 % over the years, with large fluctuations). The proportion of oats needs optimised for your conditions by experience.

Further information

Further reading

- <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/32816/1/1670-koernerleguminosen-mischkulturen.pdf>
- <https://www.agrarforschungschweiz.ch/2015/11/mit-mischkulturen-die-inlaendische-eiweissversorgung-verbessern/>

Weblinks

- <https://www.bioaktuell.ch/pflanzenbau/ackerbau/mischkulturen>
- <https://www.lko.at/media.php?filename=download%3D%2F2020.02.11%2F1581422570268322.pdf&rn=Nanoviren%20-%20Ertragsausf%C3%A4lle%20bei%20Leguminosen.pdf>

About this practice abstract

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Permalink: <https://zenodo.org/uploads/15118708>

LegumES – Valorization of ecosystem services provided by legume crops - aims to share, showcase, co-develop, and implement the knowledge, key agronomic practices, methodologies, and tools which will allow optimized legume-based systems, and valorization of the ES benefits provided.

Project website: www.legumesproject.eu

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Funding

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

Project funded by

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

LegumES has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101135512. Its work is supported by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) through the Horizon Europe Guarantee scheme Grant Agreement and by the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI) under grant No. 23.00034 and 23.00645.

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union, UK Research and Innovation ((UKRI), European Research Executive Agency (REA) or the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI). Neither the European Union nor any other granting authority can be held responsible for them.